

Kinetics and mechanism of substitution studies on *cis*-diaqua-bis(bipyridyl)ruthenium(II) by dimethylglyoxime in 10% (v/v) ethanol

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Deaquation rate of *cis*-diaqua-bis(bipyridyl)ruthenium(II) by dimethylglyoxime in 10% (v/v) ethanol is independent of pH but increases with increasing [dmgH₂] and approaches a limiting value at higher [ligand]. The activation parameters have been compared with other analogous systems. The reaction rates are insensitive to the nature of the incoming ligands and a dissociative mechanism has been proposed.

The interest on ruthenium(II) chemistry is increasing due to its applications in diverse fields. Ruthenium(II) is important due to its similarities¹ with platinum(II) (e.g. *cis*-platin). In the field of ligand substitution on ruthenium(II) complexes, a lot of work has already been done². Controversy regarding mechanisms still persists. In view of this we have taken a program of studying the kinetic behavior of ruthenium(II) with different oximes. In this paper we discuss the kinetic aspects of the substitution of aqua molecules from *cis*-diaqua-bis(bipyridyl)ruthenium(II) by dimethylglyoxime.

Results and Discussion

The kinetics of the substitution reaction have been studied at 410 nm, λ_{max} for the product complex **2**. Here the spectral difference between the reactant **1** and **2** is maximum. The time scan spectra (Fig. 1) show the presence of isosbestic points and indicate a single product. The composition of the product in solution was determined by Job's method of continuous variation. The M : L ratio was found to be 1 : 1.

Effect of [Ru(bipy)(H₂O)₂]²⁺ on rate constant : At a constant ligand concentration (9.5×10^{-4} mol dm⁻³), pH (4.5), temperature (50°) and ionic strength (0.1 mol dm⁻³), $10^5 k_{\text{obs}}$ values are 5.35, 5.5 and 5.3 s⁻¹ at $10^5 [1] = 3.8, 5.7$ and 7.6 mol dm⁻³, i.e. the reaction is first order with respect to [1],

$$d[2]/dt = k_{\text{obs}}[1] \quad (1)$$

Variation of rate constant with pH : At a fixed [1] (9.5×10^{-5} mol dm⁻³), [ligand] (23.75×10^{-4} mol dm⁻³), ionic strength (0.1 mol dm⁻³) and temperature (50°), the $10^5 k_{\text{obs}}$ values remain almost the same at pH 3.5, 4.0, 4.5, 5.0 and

Fig. 1. Time-scan spectra of the reaction between dimethylglyoxime and *cis*-[Ru(bipy)₂(H₂O)₂]²⁺ : (A, B, C, D, E, F) at 20 min time interval; [Ru(bipy)₂(H₂O)₂]²⁺ = 9.5×10^{-5} mol dm⁻³, [dmgH₂] = 19.0×10^{-4} mol dm⁻³, cell used = 1 cm quartz, pH = 4.5 and temp. = 50°.

5.5. The pK values of the complex and the ligand at 25° are

Hence, in the experimental pH range, the complex mainly exists in the diaqua form and the ligand is present in the neutral dmgH_2 form and we observe negligible dependence of k_{obs} on the pH.

Effect of $[\text{dmgH}_2]$ on rate : The concentration of $[\text{dmgH}_2]$ was varied from 9.5×10^{-4} to 47.5×10^{-4} mol dm^{-3} at a constant $[\text{I}]$ (9.5×10^{-5} mol dm^{-3}), pH (4.5) and ionic strength (0.1 mol dm^{-3}). The results are collected in

Fig. 2. Effect of $[\text{dmgH}_2]$ on rate constant (k_{obs}) at different temperatures : (A) 45, (B) 50, (C) 55 and (D) 60°.

Table I. The rate increases with increase in $[\text{dmgH}_2]$ and approaches a limiting value at higher $[\text{ligand}]$ (Fig. 2). The study at even higher $[\text{dmgH}_2]$ was restricted by the poor solubility of the ligand. From the experimental findings Scheme I is proposed.

Table I. Values of k_{obs} (s^{-1}) at different temperatures and various $[\text{dmgH}_2]$

$[\text{I}] = 9.5 \times 10^{-5}$ mol dm^{-3} , pH = 4.5, $\mu = 0.1$ mol dm^{-3}

$10^4 [\text{dmgH}_2]$ mol dm^{-3}	$10^5 k_{\text{obs}}$ (s^{-1}) at			
	45°	50°	55°	60°
9.50	1.3	1.8	3.2	5.9
14.25	2.0	2.7	4.5	9.1
19.00	2.5	3.4	5.7	10.7
23.75	3.3	4.5	7.4	15.5
28.50	3.6	5.0	9.5	16.7
38.00	4.5	6.4	12.3	20.8
47.50	5.6	7.7	13.3	23.2

Scheme 1

If we apply steady state approximation to the five-coordinate transition state, we obtain eqn. (4)

$$\text{Rate} = k_1 k_2 [\text{I}] [\text{dmgH}_2] / (k_{-1} + k_2 [\text{dmgH}_2]) \quad (4)$$

The second order rate observed for the reaction is consistent with the limiting mechanism. When $k_{-1} \gg k_2 [\text{dmgH}_2]$, eqn. (4) reduces to

$$\text{Rate} = (k_1 k_2 / k_{-1}) [\text{Ru}(\text{bipy})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2^{2+}] [\text{dmgH}_2] \quad (5)$$

which explains why second order rate is observed at lower concentration of the ligand. But at the high concentration of the ligand, i.e. $k_2 [\text{dmgH}_2] \gg k_{-1}$, the limiting rate (6) is obtained,

$$\text{Rate} = k_1 [\text{Ru}(\text{bipy})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2^{2+}] \quad (6)$$

Comparing this equation with the rate expression obtained by varying $[\text{I}]$ it can be written as

$$\text{Rate} = k_{\text{obs}} [\text{I}] \quad (7)$$

$$k_{\text{obs}} = k_1 k_2 [\text{dmgH}_2] / (k_{-1} + k_2 [\text{dmgH}_2]) \quad (8)$$

$$\text{or, } 1/k_{\text{obs}} = 1/k_1 + (k_{-1}/k_1 k_2 [\text{dmgH}_2]) \quad (9)$$

The terms k_{-1} and k_2 indicate the relative reactivities of the solvent water and the ligand dmgH_2 for the pentacoordinated reaction intermediate. A plot of $1/k_{\text{obs}}$ against $1/[\text{dmgH}_2]$ gives a straight-line with an intercept. The values of k_1 and k_{-1}/k_2 were obtained from the intercepts and ratios of the slope to intercept. These values are compared with analogous systems (Table 2).

Effect of temperature on the reaction rate : The reaction was studied at four different temperatures in 10% (v/v) ethanol-water medium. The activation parameters (ΔH^\ddagger and ΔS^\ddagger) were calculated from Eyring plot and compared with other systems (Table 3). The activation parameters are similar for different incoming ligands indicating that the dissociation step (slow) is only important and incoming ligands have only little influence on the energetics of the activated complex formation.

Table 2. Values of k_1 and k_{-1}/k_2 for the anation of $[\text{Ru}(\text{bipy})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]^{2+}$ with different ligands at different temperatures

Ligand	Medium	pH	Temp. (°C)	$10^4 k_1$ s ⁻¹	$10^3 k_{-1}/k_2$	Ref.
Pyridine-2-aldoxime	Aqueous	4.5	45	3.6	14.5	5
			50	5.0	13.3	
			55	8.0	12.5	
			60	—	—	
Acetylacetone	Aqueous	6.0	45	3.4	7.3	6
			50	5.3	7.0	
			55	7.7	6.8	
			60	—	—	
L-Cysteine	Aqueous	5.5	45	—	—	7
			50	5.0	62.5	
			55	8.0	50.0	
			60	10.0	45.0	
8-Hydroxyquinoline	10% (v/v) EtOH- H ₂ O	6.0	45	3.6	3.5	8
			50	5.0	3.3	
			55	—	—	
			60	—	—	
dmgH ₂	10% (v/v) EtOH- H ₂ O	4.5	45	4.4	32.0	Present work
			50	5.7	28.0	
			55	8.0	24.0	
			60	13.3	21.0	

Table 3. Values of ΔH^\ddagger and ΔS^\ddagger for the anation of *cis*- $[\text{Ru}(\text{bipy})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]$ with different ligands

System	ΔH^\ddagger (kJ mol ⁻¹)	$-\Delta S^\ddagger$ (JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹)	Ref.
<i>cis</i> - $[\text{Ru}(\text{bipy})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]^{2+}$ / pyridine-2-aldoxime	59.6	124	5
/acetylacetone	61.0	119	6
/L-cysteine	64.0	111	7
/8-hydroxyquinoline	67.0	101	8
/dmgH ₂	64.0	110	Present work

Conclusion : In the proposed mechanism (Scheme 1) one aqua molecule dissociates in a slow step forming a pentacoordinated intermediate which can react with either water or dmgH₂. The coordination of the dmgH₂ by one nitrogen to the ruthenium(II) centre of the intermediate facilitate the expulsion of the second aqua molecule. In the second step (fast) chelation of the dmgH₂ occurs by release of the second aqua molecule and one proton from the ligand.

Experimental

The complex *cis*- $[\text{Ru}(\text{bipy})_2(\text{CO}_3)] \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ was prepared by the reported method⁹ and characterized by elemental analyses and spectral data (the characteristics of the MLCT band is $\lambda_{\text{max}} = 485 \text{ nm}$, $\epsilon = 7700$), in agreement with the literature data¹⁰. The diaqua complex **1** was prepared *in situ* by acidification (*p*-toluenesulfonic acid was used since it did not oxidize the substrate complex to Ru^{III}). Dimethylglyoxime was of A.R. quality. The product of the reaction between complex **1** and dimethylglyoxime could not be isolate, but the stoichiometry in solution was determined by mixing them in different molar ratios, viz. 1 : 1, 1 : 2, 1 : 3,

1 : 4 and 1 : 5 each at pH 4.5 and thermostated in a water-bath at 55° for 48 h. The absorption spectra of all the solutions exhibited the same λ_{max} (410 nm) and almost same absorbances. The composition of the product in solution was determined by Job's method of continuous variation. The metal-ligand ratio was found to be 1 : 1. The pH of the solution was adjusted by adding NaOH/*p*-toluenesulfonic acid and measured by a Systronics 335 pH-meter. Double-distilled water was used throughout. All other chemicals used were of A.R. grade or purified before use. The rate measurements were carried out on a Shimadzu UV-2101 PC fitted with a thermobath (Shimadzu TB 85) at 410 nm, where a substantial difference existed between the reactant and the product complex. Conventional mixing technique was used and pseudo-first order conditions maintained throughout the course of the reaction. The pseudo-first order rate constants (k_{obs}) were determined graphically from the plot of $\ln(A_\infty - A_0)/(A_\infty - A_t)$ versus time, where A_0 , A_t and A_∞ are absorbances at the outset, at time t and at infinite time or after completion of the reaction. The reaction was studied in 10% (v/v) ethanol. The reported rate data represented as an average of duplicate runs are reproducible within $\pm 4\%$.

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References

1. M. Zhao and M. J. Clarke, *J. Biol. Inorg. Chem.*, 1999, **4**, 325; E. Galardon, P. Lc. Maux, A. Bondon and G. Simonneaux, *Tetrahedron : Asym.*, 1999, **10**, 4203; C. Pitteri and R. Cini, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 1998, 325; K. B. Reddy, M. P. Cho, J. F. Wishart, J. J. Emgly and S. S. Isied, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1996, **35**, 7241.
2. N. Aebischer, N. R. Churlaud, L. Dolci, U. Frey and A. E. Merbach, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1998, **37**, 5915; M. H. Schmidt, G. Horton and I. Tong, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1998, **37**, 5948; B. Chakraborty and U. K. Kar, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1994, **33**, 1024; J. Chakravarty and S. Bhattacharya, *Proc. Indian Acad. Sci., Chem. Sci.*, 1995, **107**, 361; N. Lima, S. Benedito, D. Franco and R. V. Eldik, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 1995, 463; J. N. Armor and H. Taube, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1970, **92**, 6170; R. E. Shephard and H. Taube, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1973, **12**, 1392; J. C. N. Filho and D. W. Franco, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 1980, **113**, 55; J. M. A. Hoddenbagh and D. H. Macartney, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1986, **25**, 380; J. F. Ojo, O. Olubuyide and O. Oyetunji, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 1987, 957; N. R. Davies and T. L. Mullins, *Aust. J. Chem.*, 1968, **21**, 915; H. E. Toma and J. M. Malin, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1972, **94**, 4039; C. M. Lieber, M. H. Schmidt and N. S. Lewis, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1986, **108**, 6103.
3. L. R. Allen, B. Durhan and J. Walsh, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1987, **26**, 53.
4. "Stability Constants of Metal-ion Complexes", Compiled by L. G.

- Sillen and A. E. Martell, Spl. pub. no. 17, The Chemical Society, London 1964.
5. D. Mallick and G. S. De, *Transition Met. Chem.*, 1993, **18**, 417.
 6. D. Mallick and G. S. De, *Transition Met. Chem.*, 1992, **17**, 491.
 7. D. Mallick and G. S. De, *Transition Met. Chem.*, 1992, **17**, 34.
 8. D. Mallick and G. S. De, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Jpn.*, 1992, **65**, 609.
 9. E. C. Johnson, B. P. Sullivan, D. J. Salmon, S. A. Adeyemi and T. J. Meyer, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1978, **17**, 2211.
 10. N. R. Davies and T. L. Mullins, *Aust. J. Chem.*, 1967, **20**, 657.